

Supplementary materials: Land use

Land use classifications

Table S1: Classification of CORINE land use classes, land use classes used in model training and land use classes in the future land use maps

CORINE land use classes (44 types)	Land use classes used to train our model (14 types)	Land use classes in future land use maps (5 types)
1 – Continuous urban fabric 2 – Discontinuous urban fabric	Urban	Urban
3 – Industrial or commercial units 4 – Road and rail networks and associated land 5 – Port areas 6 – Airports	Industry, commerce and transport	Urban
7 – Mineral extraction sites 8 – Dump sites 9 – Construction sites	Mine, dump and construction	Urban
10 – Green urban areas 11 – Sport and leisure facilities	Urban green	Urban
12 – Non-irrigated arable land 13 – Permanently irrigated land 14 – Rice fields	Arable	Crops
15 - Vineyards 16 – Fruit trees and berry plantations 17 – Olive groves	Permanent crops	Crops
18 – Pastures	Pasture	Pasture
19 – Annual crops associated with permanent crops 20 – Complex cultivation patterns 21 - Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation 22 – Agro-forestry areas	Other rural	Crops
23 – Broad-leaved forest 24 – Coniferous forest 25 – Mixed forest	Forest	Forest
26 – Natural grasslands 27 – Moors and heathland 28 – Sclerophyllous vegetation 29 - Transitional woodland shrub	Vegetation	Non-forest nature
30 – Beaches, dunes and sands 31 – Bare rocks 32 – Sparsely vegetated areas 33 – Burnt areas 34 – Glaciers and perpetual snow	Open unvegetated	Non-forest nature
35 – Inland marshes 36 – Peat bogs	Inland wetlands	Non-forest nature
40 – Water courses	Inland water	NA

41 – Water bodies		
37 – Salt marshes 38 – Salines 39 – Intertidal flats	Marine water and wetlands	Non-forest nature
42 – Coastal lagoons 43 – Estuaries 44 – Sea and ocean	Marine water and wetlands	NA

Converting future land use classes into the classes used for model training

The land use classification used in model training had 14 land use types, while the future land use maps had just 5 types (see table S1). In order to use the future land use maps, they had to be converted to the 14-type classification. Here we describe the procedure we followed to do this. The code to run this is also available in the supplementary materials.

Available data

We used the CORINE 2006 land use map as our reference (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2020), since this is roughly in the middle of the reference period we used when making predictions (1991-2020). This was easily converted into the 14-type classification using the table above. This map is available on a 100m grid.

Future land use maps for 2050 were taken from the Dutch One Health SSPs (Dellar et al., 2024, n.d.). There are four alternative maps, one for each scenario, each on a 1km grid. These maps do not include water, since they made the assumption that there would be no significant changes in water over this time period.

Defining the problem

We can imagine a simplified system where we have 3 future land use types: A, B and C. Each of these comprises 3 different sub-types which are used in the reference period:

$$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \in A$$

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 \in B$$

$$\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3 \in C$$

For example, if A was the ‘crops’ type from our 5-type classification in table S1, α_1, α_2 and α_3 might be ‘arable’, ‘permanent crops’ and ‘other rural’ from the 14-type classification.

A given grid-cell might have buffers looking like this in the reference and future maps:

Figure S1: A simplified schematic of possible buffers for reference and future land use.

The challenge then is to represent the future land use as an appropriate combination of $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \gamma_1, \gamma_2$ and γ_3 .

General approach

The future land use in the 14-type classification is made up of different components:

- Water
- Land use types which were present in the reference but which are no longer present in the future (i.e. β_1, β_2 in figure S1) (we call these 'type R')
- Land use types which were present in the reference and which are still represented in the future (i.e. α_1 in figure S1) ('type RF')
- Land use types which were not present in the reference but which are represented in the future (i.e. $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3$ in the above example) ('type F')

We created a procedure to assign values to these four components (as described below). We had to made two adjustments:

- (i) Adjustment because there is not a perfect mapping between the 14-type and 5-type classifications, since 'marine water and wetlands' counts as both 'water' and 'non-forest nature'. This was performed as part of the procedure to assign values to the four components (details below).
- (ii) Adjustment based on the scenarios themselves, since some are defined as having more 'urban green' within their urban areas than others. This was performed after the values of the four components had been assigned.

Procedure

The following procedure is applied to each grid square and each buffer size.

Step 1: Add water to future land use

The total area of water within the buffer was calculated. This was taken from the CORINE 2006 map (types 40-44) and included both inland water and marine water. The proportions of the future land use types (e.g. A and C in figure S1) were reduced proportionally. We can call these adjusted proportions \hat{A} and \hat{C} .

Figure S2: Step 1 - adding water to future land use.

Step 2: Land use types which were present in the reference but which are no longer present in the future ('Type R')

While it is tempting simply to ignore these land use types, in reality it seems possible that a small proportion of them would remain. For example, a forest might be chopped down for urban development, but they may keep some small wooded areas. Such areas would not necessarily show up in the future land use maps, since they use a much coarser grid than the reference.

We first calculate the total future area taken up by type R. We define this as:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \text{minimum} \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{Sum of all type R} \\ \text{areas in reference} \end{array} , \begin{array}{l} \text{Each individual land} \\ \text{use proportion in} \\ \text{future land use} \end{array} , 0.8 \right)$$

We used this formula because it ensures that the total future area taken up by type R is:

- Less than it was in the reference period (because it no longer shows up in the future land use map)
- Less than any future land use type (because the future land use types do appear in the future land use map and type R doesn't, suggesting that type R take up less area)
- Less than half the total area (as the maximum it can be is 0.4. If it was more than half then it would appear in the future land use map)

In our example, this would be:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \text{minimum} ((\beta_1 + \beta_2), \hat{A}, \hat{C}, 0.8)$$

We can then then divide this between all the type R land use types by scaling them, keeping them in the same relative proportions. In our example these are β_1 and β_2 . Our future land use under the 14-type classification now looks like this, where the 'A/C-types' represents a combination of A and C types, still to be determined:

Figure S3: Step 2 – add land use types which were present in the reference but which are no longer present in the future.

Step 3: Land use types which were present in the reference and which are still represented in the future ('Type RF')

We first determine the total area assigned to type RF. To do this, the remaining unassigned area (i.e. the white space in figure 3) is split between the future land use types (A and C), keeping them in the same relative proportions. Here we are concerned with future land use types which include a land use type which was present in the reference (i.e. A). These are simply assigned their reference land use types (i.e. α_1), keeping the proportions the same if there is more than one.

There was a slight complication if one of these reference land use types was 'Marine water and wetlands', since marine water is already included in 'Water', while marine wetlands are not. If this was the case, then the marine water was removed from 'Water' and added to 'Marine water and wetlands', while the remaining water was counted as 'Inland water'. If 'Marine water and wetlands' was not included in the reference land use types, then the whole of the 'Water' section was counted as 'Inland water'.

Figure S4: Step 3 – add land use types which were present in the reference and which are still represented in the future.

Step 4: Land use types which were not present in the reference but which are represented in the future ('Type F')

Here we have little information to work with, so we assume that there is some amount of all possible land use types. In our example, there are no elements of land use type C in the reference, so we

assume that there is a small part of all land use types which are represented in C, i.e. γ_1, γ_2 and γ_3 . The relative proportions of these types were based on the national average. E.g. if nationally there was twice as much γ_1 as γ_2 , then we would use twice as much γ_1 as γ_2 in our buffer.

The one exception was for ‘Marine water and wetlands’, which were never added unless they were present in the reference.

Figure S5: Step 4 – add land use types which were not present in the reference but which are represented in the future.

Step 5: Adjustment for urban greening

In the scenario narratives (Dellar et al., 2024), SSPs 1 and 5 are described as having more green spaces in urban areas. To account for this, in these two scenarios, for buffers containing ‘Urban’ or ‘Industry, commerce and transport’, we increased the proportion of ‘Urban green’ at the expense of these two types. The increase was either 5% of the existing ‘Urban green’, or 5% of the existing ‘Urban’ plus ‘Industry, commerce and transport’, whichever was larger (based on EU recommendations(European Commission, 2022)).

Creating future maps of grass and tree cover

Maps of grass and tree cover were taken from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and were available on a 100m grid (CLMS, 2020a, 2020b). To make future maps, we first calculated the average grass and tree cover under the current situation for each of the 14 land use types used in this study. These are shown in table S2.

Table S2: Average values of grass and tree cover for each of the 14 land use types, based on data from 2018

Land use type	Average grass cover (%)	Average tree cover (%)
Urban	5.8	10.9
Industry, commerce and transport	6.6	6.9
Mine, dump and construction	10.3	4.2
Urban green	22.3	27.1
Arable	10.0	4.0
Permanent crops	16.3	25.5
Pasture	66.9	6.1
Other rural	32.7	11.8

Forest	2.4	67.4
Vegetation	27.4	14.5
Open unvegetated	0.0	0.0
Inland wetlands	21.9	13.0
Inland water	0.8	1.4
Marine water and wetlands	0.0	0.0

To make the future maps for the 500m buffer, we compared current land use against future land use. If it was unchanged, we kept the current values for grass and tree cover. If the land use did change, we used the average values shown in table S2 for the new land use types. Maps for the larger buffer sizes were calculated from the 500m buffer maps.

References

- CLMS, 2020a. Grassland 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2909/60639d5b-9164-4135-ae93-fb4132bb6d83>
- CLMS, 2020b. Tree Cover Density 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2909/486f77da-d605-423e-93a9-680760ab6791>
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2020. CORINE Land Cover (CLC) 2006 (raster 100m), version 2020_20u1. <https://doi.org/10.2909/08560441-2fd5-4eb9-bf4c-9ef16725726a>
- Dellar, M., Geerling, G., Kok, K., van Bodegom, P., Schrama, S., Boelee, E., 2024. Creating the Dutch One Health Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs). *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 24, 16. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-023-02169-1>
- Dellar, M., Geerling, G., Kok, K., van Bodegom, P., van der Schrier, G., Schrama, M., Boelee, E., n.d. Future land use maps for the Netherlands based on the Dutch One Health Shared Socio-economic Pathways. Submitted.
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